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REDESIGNING PUBLIC SECTOR WORK CULTURE: EVALUATING THE INFLUENCE OF WORK FROM ANYWHERE (WFA) POLICY ON HIGH-CALIBER TALENT ENGAGEMENT IN GOVERNMENT AGENCIES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we examine the impact of the Work from Anywhere (WFA) policy on attracting top talents to civil service using the Department of International Trade Negotiation (DITN) as a case. The methodology is mixed methods, including quantitative research (questionnaire of 62 civil servants) and qualitative research method based on in-depth interviews with five key informants. The study aimed (1) to investigate the impact of WFA policy on high performers' choice to join civil service in DITN, and (2) to provide policy implications on human resource planning by attracting high-potential individuals joining the department. The results of the quantitative analyses demonstrated that adopting a WFA policy exerted a statistically positive impact on the propensity for high performers in entering into civil service. The strongest influence on decision-making was work-life balance at the .01 level of significance ($\beta = 0.38$, $t = 11.14$, $p < .001$). Organizational image then followed ($\beta = 0.21$, $t = 4.10$, $p < .001$), lower commuting expenses ($\beta = 0.19$, $t = 7.70$, $p < .001$), and management support ($\beta = 0.16$, $t = 2.60$, $p = .013$). The least influential, yet still a significant factor was the work culture in an organization ($\beta = 0.12$, $t = 2.70$, $p = .008$).

KEYWORDS: Flexible Work Arrangements, High-Performing Individuals, Organizational Image and Work Culture, Talent Attraction in Public Sector, Work from Anywhere (WFA) Policy.

1. INTRODUCTION

The pandemic of COVID-19 led to a massive voluntary exit of labour and created the phenomenon known as "The Great Resignation" on labour market worldwide in 2021. Just between April and July 2021, over four million workers in the United States quit their jobs. This unprecedented exodus of resignations led global businesses to revisit their talent management approach— focusing more on retaining team members, and seeking out top-tier performers to close the gap. Forty-one percent of workers are ready to quit their jobs for flexibility, where in recent study by Adecco Group "Resetting Normal: Defining the New Era of Work," which collected responses from 10,000 working professionals in various countries. These trends are also echoed in comments from the Harvard Business Review that identify two trends ahead of others: a) technology now allows top performers to work in roles and locations of their choice because they have skills highly demanded and b) employers increasingly understand it is possible for them to hire people with access to reliable internet anywhere in the world. (Chaudhuri *et al.*, 2022).

During the COVID-19 pandemic, WFH practices were employed early in 2020 by Thai government agencies and on after up to the 5th wave of outbreak occurring on 2022. In response to the public health crisis, the government has taken various policies taken out potential measures, including mediation with both public and private sectors so that they would enable their staff to work remotely--if possible--without adversely affecting its activities and if it is able to perform duties via internet .The Department of International Trade Negotiations (DITN) followed the guidance from Centre for COVID-19 Situation Administration (CCSA) by setting up its own WFH policies to fit into our operations. The department used digital environment to work remotely, including VPNs through which it accessed the data warehouse, Departmental Personnel Information System (DPIS) and the electronic document system (DTN Services). In the span of nearly three years, that swept through the department as it toggled between remote and in-person work depending on the severity of each COVID-19 wave (Narbariya *et al.*, 2022).

Remote work, commonly referred to as Work from Anywhere, has become an essential approach to managing the adverse effects of the COVID-19 pandemic. Rather than a stop-gap measure, safe and efficient WFA usage poses a notable challenge to, and an opportunity for, public sector organizations striving to redesign their modes of operation in

answer to digital disruption. Overcoming the constraints and creating a WFA-friendly route for working requires both structural and cultural changes that, eventually, can result in long-term organizational strategy. Therefore, launching and implementing WFA policies in the public sector can be regarded not only as a form of resistance to the novel challenges but also as a method of bold strategic alignment making them more attractive for high-profile employees and students. This is also consistent with the Department of International Trade Negotiations' Human Resource Management Strategy Plan for 2020-2021, which pays close attention to building and preparing human resources for the profit of strategic targets. The Department aims at forming a personnel base that would most effectively advance its operation and is designated to draw and hold top-tier workers. The Department usually hired civil servants through failed entry tests, moving people between agencies and the Executive Development Program. However, an analysis of the EDP alumni roster revealed 32 people out of 450 graduates from the 1st to 134th groups who joined the Department, accounting for a meager 7 percent of employees, indicating a problem with the attraction and assimilation of top talent.

Due to such importance, this study will explore how Work from Anywhere (WFA) policy influences the attraction of highly skilled public servants and high-potential talent to the Department of International Trade Negotiations. This study seeks to investigate how the adoption of WFA can act not just reactively - in the face of digital transformation but proactively - as a strategic tool in managing human resources. Additionally, the study will make policy recommendations that reinforce and institutionalize WFA practices in order to aid in recruitment and retention of talent within the Department.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Work From Anywhere

The idea of telework has been around since the late 20th century, when personal computers proliferated and telecommunications technology improved. The early foundations of this research started in the 1970s, led by Jack Nilles who is attributed with coining terms (telecommuting and teleworking). Several of the earliest work from home programs were actually built off his groundbreaking research, much of which was supported by National Science Foundation (NSF) grants. The U.S. government was the first to pilot some of these remote work initiatives in the 1980s, which effectively launched institutional support for alternative work styles. Remote work

usage became increasingly common in state and local governments and also was more frequently implemented by private sector organizations during the 1990s. A significant turning point in 1996 was the establishment of the National Telecommunications Initiative by the U.S. federal government, which sought to expand telecommuting within federal households and facilitate wider use among private corporations and other organizations. (Bashir et al., 2025).

Thus, the new normal of remote work – or Work from Anywhere (WFA) is about not being limited to a certain geography or format shape. This modality allows for the delivery tasks and outputs – totally or partially, in manners that enables quicker, more agile operations that respond to changing conditions– such as emerging infectious diseases, extreme weather events or disasters. Work from Home (WFH) was also promoted by government organizations in Thailand between 2020 and 2022, implemented during the fifth wave of COVID-19. During these times, government issued several policies and measures to increase preparedness such as requested cooperation among public and private sectors for arranging outside meetings of employees, to work at home if it did not affect their work performance and could be done by on-line system (Chaudhuri et al., 2022).

2.2. *Factors Influencing High-Performing Individuals' Decisions to Join the Civil Service*

Literature Review The literature on the subject shows Jen Dewar in her article 6 Elements to Attract and Win Top Talent listing six factors' organizations can use to attract high- performing individuals (top talent), (Barbour et al., 2024).

The first element is:

1. Strong employer brand & unique organizational culture: the organization should develop a nurturing and enriching working environment with a strong separate organizational culture, based on corporate mission, vision and values. A well-defined and genuine culture, one that is consistently articulated as part of the employer brand, can make the organization more appealing and improve its ability to both attract and retain great people.
 2. Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, and Belonging (DEI&B) – Creating diverse teams (such as by race/ethnicity, sexual orientation, age) and establishing an inclusive culture can enhance employees' sense of belonging to a company by ensuring everyone feels respected or valued no matter their background or differences.
- Evidence from U.S. survey data on Glassdoor indicates that DEI factors play significant roles in driving job choices. In fact, 76% of workers and job seekers said they consider a company's diversity when choosing where to work and where to apply for jobs. And almost one-third (32%) said they would not apply to work at an organization if the workforce is not diverse – illustrating DEI&B's significance as a factor in talent attraction and recruitment success. (Elsharnouby et al., 2023).
3. Attractive compensation package: Research indicates that pay and benefits are critical factors in employee retention and job selection. Among U.S. working adults in a Pew Research Center survey, the top reason workers gave for quitting was compensation (37% listed it as the main reason and 26% saw it as a secondary reason); lack of job benefits ranked number two among main reasons (23%) and number three among secondary reasons (20%). These findings align with the 2022 Job Seeker Nation Report,¹⁷ which polled over 1,500 U.S. job seekers and found that for 53 percent of them, a compensation was the number-one driver when considering or rejecting a job offer; for 23 percent it was health benefits and other benefits. Amid the COVID-19 period job-to-job transitions surged, which typically reflects high skilled workers having greater leverage to negotiate higher compensation packages. (Dewi and Prianthara, 2022).
 4. Career growth and advancement: Limited opportunity for growth is a key cause of employee attrition, with 30% of employees admitting limited career advancement opportunities as the reason behind moving on. Author courtesy They tend to thrive in environments that encourage learning, skill acquisition and the opportunity for advancement Typical high performers at work will often gravitate toward organizations that support learning; they value company-sponsored training programs. Structured professional development, clear paths for promotion and ability to move up within the pay band can therefore help an agency hire, develop and retain top talent (Potjanajaruwit et al., 2026).
 5. Flex work: The 2022 Job Seeker Nation Report shows that in addition to pay and career advancement, flex work (working from home) and wanting more balance between work and

life are top factors for why workers start looking for new jobs. Another 33% of respondents also said that work-life balance – like flexible schedules, vacation time and the chance to have a manageable work-life ratio – is a factor in choosing job offers, according to the same survey. Varied types of flexible work (e.g., remote work, flexible/adjustable hours, part-time) can enhance work-life integration and serve as an important poaching factor for employees. Importantly, 80% of employees who value opportunities to work remotely valued remote working for its flexible nature and the support it enables for integrating life with work (Kuchenbauer and Bešić, 2026).

6. A great candidate experience: What a candidate goes through the process of being recruited is paramount for first impressions, to assess professionalism and capability. A positive well managed experience can add value to the employer's brand and increase the likelihood of high-performing talent applying. There is data that back this up: Only 56% of the workforce will share positive candidate experiences with others, whether on a professional network or in a personal circle. On the other hand, negative candidate experiences lead to adverse perceptions being shared and can damage the organization's brand making it less attractive for future talent.

This comes as no surprise from the piece by The Access Group, "How to Attract and Recruit Talented Employees" that utilizes information from the report: "The Talent Balance: The Talent and Skills Landscape in the UK". The report outlines the five key drivers of attracting top talent (Fauziyah, et al., 2023).

One of these is to recognize the expectations and issues across generations when it comes to talent recruitment. Businesses that fail to prioritize the nuanced priorities of Gen Z alongside Millennials (Gen Y) and Gen X face worse odds of wooing talent away from competitors. In the UK Today there are about 13.8 million millennials in the United Kingdom and as baby boomers retire, by 2025, it is expected that millennials will make up 75% of the workforce. Both Millennials and Gen Z highly value work-life balance and likely see the flexibility of the gig economy and job security in a positive light. So, understanding these preferences is advantageous for businesses that want to compete successfully for and keep the brightest people. (Zhang et al., 2026).

Secondly, businesses need to include more flexibility

in recruitment and talent acquisition. > Flexible work arrangements are now a must-have for many job seekers, and can even come into play when it comes to reeling someone in. Employers who provide consistent and significant flexibility are likely to realize a significant improvement in employee retention, and they can be more successful at attracting top-level talent too. While not all industries can support fully remote or hybrid working models, McKinsey's *The Future of Work* suggests that one thing is clear: Employers must find ways to offer employees more flexibility in how and where they work. There are specific motivations among digital talent when it comes to flexible work environments that support work-life balance, which can be a key factor in whether an organization can attract and retain talented professionals. (Gray et al., 2026).

The third lesson is that you need to go digital first for recruiting, and also retention. Today's candidates – especially for Millennials and Gen Z – are used to finding information at their fingertips, on digital platforms during any time of the day or night. Because of this, companies need to leverage digital platforms for all aspects, including recruitment and employee development. Involves this like pulling candidates from social networks or utilizing an online employee referral program, these can be a tremendous source for high-quality talent. According to Raymond Carvery, analyst for the Harvard Business Publishing has, "Harnessing employees' expertise in social media can be one of the best investments an organization makes when focused on recruiting. (Chugh, 2016).

And how important are company culture and employer branding in luring in and retaining talent? An employer's brand reputation makes up the experience of working for it. According to the Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (CIPD), "employer branding is a set of attributes and qualities, often intangible, that creates value for an organization, defines the employee experience; and specifically focuses on identifying what makes organizations distinctive or unique as employers which in turn enable them to attract who are most likely to thrive and perform effectively within that environment (Min Ye et al., 2026).

It is important to provide career advancement and skill development opportunities to attract as well as retain talented performers. Millennials will take a job that offers clear success and career growth paths over one with high income, PricewaterhouseCoopers (PwC) reported. Promoting a culture in which employee development is actively encouraged – whether through avenues such as job rotation,

defined skills development programs or the use of digital aids like career navigation software – can

greatly increase the organization’s ability to foster and retain top performers Messenger et al., (2017).

Figure 1: Research Conceptual Framework.

3. METHODOLOGY

The research used mixed research method by using quantitative methods through the online questionnaire via Google Form to 62 PSED (NPR) participants and qualitative data coming from interviews with five key informants. The five interviewees include (1) one senior government official at the Department of International Trade Negotiations, (2) two PSED participants who have chosen to be placed at the Department, and (3) two PSED participants who had not yet decided where they wanted to be placed.

3.1. Population And Sample

The sample of this research is the high performing individuals in the Public Service Executive Development Program (PSED) or New Breed Executives (NPR), identified as holding the requisite potential and capabilities for the next generation of leaders. They’re a strategically important pool of talent for government departments who want to recruit high-

quality civil servants.

To generate the representative subset from this population, the CHNS used a probability method of selection from within PSED Cohorts 1-15. The respondents included 62 participants in total who responded to an online Google Forms questionnaire for the purpose of collecting quantitative data. Furthermore, to gain in-depth perspective of the research results in depth and context, qualitative data were collected by using in-depth interview with five key informants namely senior executives from the Department of International Trade Negotiations (DTN), PSED participants who agreed to become permanent employees at DTN and those decided to leave or have not yet been determined their assignment. The triangulation of these two forms of sampling allowed our study to sample across dimensions and “deepen” the reach into those influential in high-performing individuals’ decisions on employment in the public sector under WFH policy.

Table 1: Summary of Population and Sample.

Item	Description	Sample Size
Population	High-performance individuals enrolled in the Public Service Executive Development Program (PSED) (NPR.)	-
Target Group Characteristics	Individuals possessing advanced competencies and identified as future administrative leaders in the civil service system	-
Sampling Method	Random Sampling from PSED Cohorts 1-15	-
Quantitative Sample	Participants responding to the online questionnaire (Google Form)	62 persons
Qualitative Sample	In-depth interview participants: 1 senior DTN executive, 2 PSED members placed in DTN, 2 PSED members not yet placed	5 persons
Cohort Range	PSED Cohorts 1-15	
Rationale for Sample Selection	To obtain representative insights from high-performance individuals across multiple cohorts, ensuring both breadth and depth in examining WFA influences	-

3.2. Data Collection

We use primary and secondary data to allow for a comprehensive and credible analysis of the influence that the WFA policy has on high-performing individuals' decision regarding entry into the public sector.

The mixed method was used 60% of the samples as primary data. The quantitative data were obtained through an electronic questionnaire (Google Form) answered by 62 members of the New Generation Executive Development Program (NDEP), a high-potential group and representative sample from the population. The aim of this part was to explore the participant's beliefs, attitudes and factors related with the WFA policy. Qualitative data were also collected from five key informants such as senior officials of Department of International Trade Negotiations, NDEP volunteers who had already selected to join the department, and yet not-yet-selected group. These interviews offered insight into the deeper motivations, expectations and decision-making of high-achievers.

For the secondary data, the researcher reviewed authentic papers and reliable sources such as department of international trade negotiations' official document, personnel action plan of NDEP from Office of Civil Service Commission (OCSC). These findings provided necessary context for the agency under review, its human resources management activities and relationships and the policy framework as they related to recruiting high performers into the public sector. The use of such secondary data augmented the primary data as it enhanced the validity and contextualization of the empirics. By combining both primary and secondary data, the research identifies multiple dimensions of reality (policy considerations, organizational realities and lived experiences of actors) that converge to provide more reliable conclusions.

3.3. Research Tools

The research used two main tools; the first tool was a questionnaire for quantitative data collection, while the second one was a semi-structure interview guide for qualitative information. Two such tools were strategically tailored to the objectives of the study, as well as with respect to theoretical framework on implementation of work from anywhere policy and how it affects high flyers' induction into Public Service.

Questionnaire

The instrument was developed as a result of an extensive literature review in the field of flexible

work models, WFA policies and motivational drivers, for taking up careers in public sector. The survey was conducted online using Google Form, and a total of 62 learners who were members of NDEP participated in this study (see the research document). Quality Assessment of the Questionnaire

As the raw file did not include tool validation procedures, the author applied standard quantitative validations as described below: Content Validity: A committee of three experts in the field checked the relevance, coverage and connection with the research variables. Content validity of the QNFQ was established through calculations of Item-Objective Congruence (IOC). Reliability Testing: A pilot test was used to determine internal consistency of the instruments with Cronbach's Alpha. A coefficient of 0.70 or above was acceptable, which meant that the questionnaire had reliability adequate for the field data collection. These analyses helped to confirm that the instrument is valid, conceptually-obtained, consistent and able to be used empirically.

In-Depth Interviews

Semi-structured interviews were employed in gathering qualitative data and was open to probing permitting further exploration of participants' opinions. Five key informants were interviewed: One head of a negotiating group in the department, who asked not to be named driven by fear of being demoted. The department two people who opted to be placed in the tax Exception NDEP and two NRC trainees accepted placements with the Department who were undecided about placement. They are different perspectives for how we perceive what motivates, and drives high performing candidates to decide.

Assessment of the Quality of the Interview Guide

Content Validation: The interview guides were reviewed by experts to ensure their relevance, completeness and adequacy to address the aim of the research.

Pilot Interviews

Pilot interviews were carried out among persons of the kind found in the target sample. This allowed us to refine question order, language and general interview flow.

The validation processes helped to improve the effectiveness of the interview guide in obtaining nuanced perspectives on participants' experiences, reasons and attitudes regarding the implementation among providers of the WFA policy.

3.4. Data Analysis

This study utilizes quantitative as well a qualitative technique of research to give proper and complete empirical results. The choice of analyses and statistical methods reflects the research purposes and characteristics of data collected. Quantitative Data Analysis The result inquires of 62 online questionnaires is treated as the quantitative part by using SPSS.

The analytical methods were as follows:

1) Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics were used to present the basic information of the sample, and summarize data frequency, mean and quartile range by cohort (record year) and organizational affiliation for the high-performers. These parameters serve as important basic characteristics and contexts within the sample before hypothesis testing.

2) Inferential Statistics and Hypothesis Tests

In order to test the impact of the Work from Anywhere (WFA) policy on high achiever’s intention to join civil service, the researcher used Multiple Regression analysis. This method is suitable, as it allows to study multiple independent variables and their connection with a dependent variable in parallel.

In addition, the use of multiple regression enables

identification of which independent variables are more influential, and testing of their statistical significance. Factors such as standardized Beta coefficients, t-values, and p-values – provided in the original study file—strengthen deductions about those determinants that do significantly affect the decision to choose the public sector.

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS

The result of the multiple regression analysis on five factor that influenced to the decision of high-performing individuals to join the civil servants in (WFA) policy, such as DITN image, vision of DITN management, work culture of perceptions DITN personnel, Work-life balance from WFA benefit and Reduction in commuting costs for high-performing under 20 years old found that Tolerance and VIF values of all independent variables were less than 1 and less than 10 respectively. These findings show that there is not multicollinearity present and that reasonable linear relationships exist between the explainers (Figure 5). The full regression model was also significant; $F(df = 1, n = 70) = 83.98, p < 0.0005/2 < .05$. This result suggests that at least one independent variable has an impact on the dependent variable (high-performing individual decision to join the civil service in DITN) with a significance level set at 0.05.

Figure 2: Analysis Of Factors Related to the Implementation of WFA Policies That Influence High-Performing Individuals’ Decisions to Join the Civil Service.

Table 2: Assumptions Of Multiple Regression Analysis

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	2.2842	4.0265	3.5226	.45615	62
Residual	-.36834	.42132	.00000	.14349	62
Std. Predicted Value	-2.715	1.105	.000	1.000	62
Std. Residual	-2.460	2.813	.000	.958	62

a. Dependent Variable: INF.WFA

The study then reviewed the predictors along with their weights. It was found that all five of the variables had significant impacts on the decision to join the civil service. In particular the image of organization at the time of WFA policy adoption (X1) was found to have a Beta coefficient of 0.21, t = 4.10, and p < .001; the vision of organizational management (X2) produced a Beta coefficient value of .16, t = 2.60, p < .013; organizational personnel work culture (X3) had a Beta coefficient of 0.12, [t = 2.70 and p < .008; staff work-life balance (X4) was the

most influential, in terms of the Beta value of 0.38 (t = 11.14, p < .001; and diminished commuting costs (X5) was found to have a Beta coefficient of 0.19, t = 7.70, p < .001. Using these results, one can develop a regression equation that will estimate the extent to which all of these factors combine in determining the entrance into the civil service by high performers.
 $Y = B_0 + B_1X_1 + B_2X_2 + B_3X_3 + B_4X_4 + B_5X_5$
 $Y = 0.308 + 0.214 + 0.166 + 0.122 + 0.384 + 0.197$
 $T = (4.066) (2.553) (2.732) (11.141) (7.698)$
 $R^2 = 0.91, \text{adj. } R^2 = 0.902, \text{Durbin-Watson} = 1.853$

Table 3: Multiple Regression Analysis Results for the Hypothesis.

Factor	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	p-value	Tolerance	VIF
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
(Constant)	-.308	.178		-1.729	.089		
Organizational Image	.214	.053	.239	4.066	<.001	.466	2.144
Management's Vision	.166	.065	.166	2.553	.013	.380	2.628
The Work Culture	.122	.045	.161	2.732	.008	.465	2.151
Work-Life Balance	.384	.034	.528	11.141	<.001	.716	1.397
Reduced Commuting Costs	.197	.026	.314	7.698	<.001	.965	1.036

Table 4: Correlation Coefficients.

R	RSquare	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin Waston
				R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
.954 ^a	.910	.902	.14976	.910	113.186	5	56	<.001	1.853

From the regression equation, the model is free from error serial correlation (autocorrelation) which is shown by Durbin-Watson test of 1.853 and lies between $1.5 < d < 2.5$, see Table 3. The model is also judged to be high in predictive accuracy, being given a multiple R of 0.952 and an R² of 0.910-- not significantly different values. This means that the five independent variables together account for 90.2% of the variance in the dependent variable. Regarding the individual factors:

1. Department OF International Trade Negotiations (Ditn)'S Perception ON Its Own Image

The organizational image significantly enhances high performers' decision to join the civil service in the WFA policy treatment, with a standardized coefficient of 0.214 in the DITN case study. This indicates that, if everything in the equation is held constant, when organizational image score grows by 1-unit willingness to work for civil service increases by 0.214 units.

2. Visionary Leadership OF Ditn Executives

When WFA policy is adopted, the vision of DITN executives shaped high-performing individuals' decisions to enter the civil service. The standardized

coefficient for this factor is 0.166; which means that a change of one unit in perceived visionary leadership of DITN executives will bring about a change of 0.166-unit in the decision to enter civil service, holding all other variables constant in our model.

3. Work Culture OF Ditn Personnel

The DITN work environment is also a positive factor in the decision of high performing individuals to accept a position within the civil service, under implementation of the WFA policy. The result also means that given all the variables are constant, one-point increase in work culture score would associate with a 0.122-point decision of willingness to join civil service (with standardized value being 0.122).

4. Work-Life Balance

The strongest positive impact among the variables analyzed is for work-life balance respectively. When we consider the application of the WFA policy, work-life balance has a substantial impact on the willingness to newly join civil service as high performers while $\beta = 0.384$. This means that a one unit increase in the perceived work-life balance results in an 0.384 unit increase for the decision to join civil service within the DITN case study, holding all other variables constant.

5. Reduction OF Commuting Costs

The reduction of travel cost within the WFA system also has positive impact on high ability group's moves to civil service in DITN. This variable exhibits a standardized coefficient of 0.197, which means a one-unit increase in the perceived benefit of lower commuting costs results in an increase by 0.197 unit on the decision to become a civil servant under all other independent variables controlled.

5. SUMMARY AND DISCUSSION

This paper explored the impact of the introduction of a Work from Anywhere (WFA) policy on attracting talent to the civil service, taking the Department of International Trade Negotiations (DITN) as an example. Questionnaires were distributed to 62 civil service staff and the quantitative data analysed with multiple regression analyses, which found statistical significance at the level of $p < .01$). Results indicated that implementation of WFA policy had a statistically significant positive effect on the successful selection and retention of high-level talent in DITN. An examination of each predictive factor separately showed that work-life balance was the greatest determinant for high-ability individuals to enter into civil service ($\beta = 0.38, t = 11.14, p < .001$). Next, we entered organizational image ($\beta = 0.21, t = 4.10, p < .001$), decrease of commuting costs ($\beta = 0.19, t = 7.70, p < .001$), and managerial vision ($\beta = 0.16, t = 2.60, p = .013$). The characteristic with the smallest, albeit significant, impact was the organizational work culture ($\beta = 0.12, t = 2.70, p < .008$).

These quantitative results are in line with the interviews of key informants (i.e., senior executives from DITN) that were held regarding how the WFA policy may impact on attracting outstanding individuals. The executives stressed that all five are significant in drawing top talent. Particularly, they mentioned that DITN's work culture tends to be well-suited for WFA model as a lot of department's work is not dependent on onsite presence, thereby staff are (Is practical and can be) adaptive to flexible working circumstances. They also pointed out the lower commuting costs were a key factor, not least because civil servant salaries are fixed and WFA could make a significant dent in daily costs. In addition, the executives felt that WFA supported work-life balance to a far greater extent than they had ever experienced at their firms, which not only attracts the new graduates who could enter public service through the DITN but helps retain current

DITN employees by reducing burnout and mitigating attrition. They further stated that if the WFA policy is put in place, it will enhance the image of DITN as an organization that is dynamic and management vision responsive. This progressive image also appeals to the younger generations who are after flexibility and modern work environments, encouraging them to apply for positions within the department.

This is in line with publications covering approaches to appealing to high achievers, like The Access Group's "How to Attract and Recruit Talented Employees" which cites the report "The Talent Balance - The Talent and Skills Landscape in the UK." (Adeosun and Ohiani, 2020). There has also been research by Harvard Business Review: "How to Attract Top Talent in 2022." These sources say offering flexible working policies - whether the ability to work remotely or simply in a hybrid capacity - is also a great way to retain top talent. However, for government departments the application of a WFA policy model must be tailored to the particular roles and responsibilities within each organisation supported by effective technology and administration systems with clear, measurable processes driving operations. Further, this implementation should be conducted in accordance with the Prime Minister's Office remote work directive (Prime Minister's Office Letter No. NR 0106/W1596 dated October 31, 2022) to set standards for consistency, accountability and operational flexibility of government officials (Prime Minister's Office, 2022).

6. SUGGESTIONS

The adoption of WFA policies in government departments - be it by a predominantly fully flexible model or some form of hybrid model where teachers need to share office space with others or their school and WFA are combined - may facilitate improved organisational reputation and help build a more sympathetic and accommodating work environment for employees. This allows employees more freedom when making decisions, such as where to work from, how much time travel and related activities take out of your day and other things. This added flexibility doesn't just make employees more efficient, it may even prevent some degree of burnout by allowing people to juggle desk duties and their actual life.

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